

Effect of processing parameter on the structure and magnetic properties of barium hexaferrite sputtered thin films

Santhoshkumar M, Jatinder singh, Puneet sharma*

School of Physics and Materials Science, Thapar University, Patiala-147004, Punjab, India

*puneet.sharma@thapar.edu & santhosh.kumar@thapar.edu, 9176792144

Abstract:

In the present work, high coercivity barium hexaferrite (BaM) thin films were fabricated by RF sputtering. The effect of film thickness, annealing temperature and Argon pressure on structural and magnetic properties were investigated by X-Ray diffraction pattern (XRD), Scanning electron microscope (SEM) and Vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM). Diffraction pattern confirms thickness and post annealing temperature are the two major parameters for better crystallization. SEM micrograph shows highly dense uniform films were obtained by lower argon pressure. Higher coercivity and squareness were obtained for one hour sputtered BaM thin film.

Fig. *M-H* plot for barium hexaferrite thin film